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wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This report presents the results from the stakeholder engagement activities at the pilot site in Karmøy (municipality in Rogaland county), Norway, using interactive collaborative tools and methods. Across three days and six workshop sessions in May 2025, 92 stakeholders engaged in an immersive 3D planning game, created mental models and participated in semi-structured interviews related to local wind energy planning.

The tools and methods are shown to be positively received by participants and foster discussions on the dilemmas and trade-offs in energy infrastructure planning. Environmental concerns were found to be important to avoid from both the mental models activity and the 3D planning game. The semi-structured interviews indicate that project ramifications, such as the number/height of wind turbines and municipal financial participation (among other things), influence local attitudes.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
DOP	Digital Orthophoto
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
GIS	Geographic Information System
NLOD	Norwegian Licence for Open Government Data
NVE	Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate
OSM	Open Street Map
SPSS	Statistical Product and Service Solutions
VR	Virtual Reality
WPPs	Wind Power Plants
WSI	Wind farm Sensitivity Index

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the activities and work carried out at the Norwegian pilot site in Karmøy. Over the course of three days (May 6–8, 2025), six workshops were organised, with the goal of studying perspectives on wind energy deployment and the potentials of different interactive tools and methods for stakeholder engagement.

Karmøy is a Norwegian island and a municipality in the southwestern region Rogaland, which has had a long history of wind energy development. In 2003, the neighbouring island Utsira erected two wind turbines. Since then, more wind energy has been deployed at and around Karmøy, including a test centre for floating offshore wind. The pilot site therefore represents an area where wind energy is mature and where the inhabitants of the island have been exposed to wind energy over a long period.

To study perspectives on wind energy in Karmøy three main activities were organised: 1) an immersive 3D game, designed to engage people and bring them closer to renewable energy concepts, 2) mental models, used to explore perceptions and understandings of the impacts of wind energy and 3) surveys and semi-structured interviews focusing on project ramifications and acceptance. Additional ancillary material was also collected for the project in the form of interviews and a demonstration of the WIMBY interactive map.

In total, 92 individuals with different backgrounds and familiarity of wind energy participated in one or several of the activities. In the immersive 3D planning game, participants discussed areas where wind energy should and should not be deployed. Furthermore, they developed wind farm scenarios for increased local electricity generation. Participants balanced perspectives such as environmental concerns with social implications in terms of proximity to settlements. Most participants preferred offshore regions that were far away from settlements and important bird areas, or areas that are already used for wind energy.

From the mental models that the participants created, environmental concerns were the most frequently used concept, but notions of fairness and the treatment of local communities was more prominent than in the pilot sites in Austria, Italy and Portugal.

The surveys and semi-structured interviews indicate that local attitudes are influenced by the project ramifications. Amelioration options, like adjusting the number and height of turbines, ensuring municipal financial participation, providing regular written updates on project progress, and involving stakeholders early in planning and siting processes can improve local attitudes.

The workshop activities were appreciated by most participants and almost 80% were positive in taking part in similar workshops in the future. Interactive tools and methods for stakeholder engagement – including early consultation, the use of VR simulations, and financial participation schemes – show promise for strengthening local trust and to enhance project acceptance.

Note to readers: This report is part of a series of four pilot studies conducted as part of the WIMBY project. Each report focuses on the respective regional results. However, to ensure the readability of each individual report, there is some minor overlap in content (e.g. process descriptions, methods).

1. Introduction

1.1 Case Study Description

Karmøy is a municipality on the west coast of Norway, with a hilly, densely populated agricultural landscape, characterised as a well-preserved holistic cultural landscape. Wind turbines have been present in the region since 2003, when two 0.6 MW turbines were built in the neighbouring municipality (and island) *Utsira*. Additional wind energy developments have since followed: Storøy, 6.4 MW in 2018; Gismarvik, 13 MW in 2021 and Tysvær, 47 MW in 2021. The region also hosts a test centre (MetCentre) for floating offshore wind, with two turbines with a combined capacity of 6 MW already built and an expansion of up to 83 MW planned. The region as such represents an area with experience of both onshore and offshore wind energy. Furthermore, the administrative region of Karmøy, Rogaland has the second highest installed capacity in Norway and the highest installed capacity per land area.

Figure 1 presents the geographic context of the Norwegian case study and highlights the locations of the 18 operational wind power plants (WPPs) in Rogaland.

The proximity to the North Sea and coastal climate leads to high wind speeds and wind power generation potential. Together with the, from a Norwegian perspective, relatively high electricity prices (Forbrukerrådet, 2025) (partly due to high domestic consumption as well as interconnectors to Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom) this makes WPPs economically attractive in the region.

Figure 1: Overview of the Karmøy pilot region and its location in Norway as well as the distribution of built and prospective WPPs. (Source: Open Street Map, Norwegian Mapping Authority, NVE, NIBIO; Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Wind energy has not been very prominent in Norway historically, largely because of the country's very good hydropower resources, which has dominated the electricity system completely. As illustrated in Figure 2, hydro power still dominates the Norwegian electricity mix and supplied between 88–92% of the electricity in the last five years. However, as the cost of

developing wind power plants dropped and domestic policies created more beneficial economic conditions, wind power became cost-competitive to Norwegian hydropower, spurring a boom in onshore wind energy development around 2017/2018 (Skjærseth et al., 2023). The rapid development triggered discussions on the (local) implications and potential conflicts with biodiversity and untouched landscapes, which culminated with the publication of a proposed national framework for wind energy by the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE). The proposal resulted in massive protests, over 5,000 written responses in the public hearing (Vasstrøm & Lysgård, 2021) and the Norwegian Government decided to temporarily stop all new licenses for WPPs in 2019. In July 2023 the processing of licensing application was resumed, and municipalities were reinstated as a planning authority in wind power siting (Vasstrøm & Lysgård, 2024).

Figure 2: Electricity generation by technology in Norway between 1993 and 2024. Data based on (Statistics Norway, 2025).

Although Rogaland has an electricity surplus of 3.2 TWh annually (largely due to high hydropower generation), the municipal balance paints a different picture, where the municipalities of Suldal and Sandnes have surpluses of 6.9 and 1.2 TWh, respectively and Karmøy, Stavanger and Tysvær have deficits of 4.0, 1.9 and 1.5 TWh, respectively (Norwegian Confederation of Trade Unions & Confederation of Norwegian Enterprises,

2023). For Karmøy, this is in part due to high-intensive industrial activities at Norsk Hydro's aluminium factory. Even if the factory in Karmøy is piloting projects with energy efficient aluminium production, the activities consume around 4 TWh of electricity annually. On top of current activities, Norsk Hydro is investing 1.65 billion NOK (~140 million EUR) in additional production capacity and a new facility for producing aluminium wire rods, used for example for transmission cables (Norsk Hydro, 2025). These new investments are important for local job creation as well as for supporting the European energy transition, but will lead to additional electricity consumption, further contributing to the power deficit in Karmøy. 110,000 tonnes of aluminium at an electricity consumption of 12.27 kWh/kg Al (for the energy-efficient aluminium) results in 1.35 TWh of additional demand for the municipality. This framework condition served as the backdrop for the planning game targets described in section 2.4.

1.2 Objective

The overarching objective of the activities in the pilot site region was to convey the multifaceted challenges associated with wind power-based electricity generation and to help stakeholders grasp its complexities through different interactive and collaborative activities. Activities organised included: 1) An immersive 3D serious planning game, 2) the creation of mental models of perceived wind energy impacts and 3) interviews detailing the link between project ramifications and acceptance.

Although these activities were also carried out at the other pilot sites (see deliverable 3.1, 3.3 and 3.4) (Giorgi et al., 2025; Schauppenlehner et al., 2025; Serôdio et al., 2025), the activities at the pilot site in Karmøy were held in a context of rapidly changing country-level attitudes to wind energy and strong community-level opposition against projects. This, together with the particular stakeholders engaged in the workshops allowed for an extended focus on the role of previous experiences and exposure to wind power developments in the region.

For the objective of the individual activities themselves, see deliverable D5.3 (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024) and D4.4 (Lowitzsch et al., 2024) for the immersive 3D serious planning game and interviews on project ramification and acceptance, respectively. The mental models activity is

complementary to the WIMBY project. Personal costs for preparation, execution, and data analysis are fully covered by a grant from the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable development, Utrecht University.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Participant engagement

To engage citizens and relevant stakeholders in the workshop activities, the recruitment featured a comprehensive mapping of stakeholders at different geographical scales (national, regional or local) (see Table 4 in the Annex for a complete list). Relevant stakeholder groups included a) university students and employees, b) environmental protection wind power opposition groups, c) industry actors, d) public sector and e) citizens/lay-people.

The Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (HVL) has a university campus in Haugesund with both research and educational activities within maritime operations and offshore wind, contributing with perspectives on future wind developments. Wind energy developments in Karmøy and the surrounding region Haugalandet¹ have faced considerable opposition and protests, partially from environmental protection and wind power opposition groups, indicating their importance in local acceptance/opposition. Industry actors such as wind energy developers and major energy consumers are also considered as important stakeholders. Together with the public sector and political actors, they set the context and agenda for new potential wind energy developments. Lastly, the perspective of citizens of Karmøy and nearby areas offer insights into how residents value different aspects, further diversifying the perspectives in the workshops.

Identified stakeholders were contacted directly and invited to participate. The primary methods for contacting the stakeholders were via e-mail and phone calls, but professional networks and public information campaigns in

¹ Haugalandet is one of four regions in Rogaland (Thorsnæs, 2024)

different forums (both in social media and together with local actors) were also carried out.

2.2 Locations

With the aim of capturing primarily local perspectives on wind energy developments in Karmøy, a balance had to be struck between the diversity of potential participants and the accessibility of the workshops when choosing the venue. There are three cities in Karmøy, namely Kopervik (population = 11,690), Åkrehamn (population = 7,955) and Skudeneshavn (population = 3,332) (Thorsnæs & Lauritzen, 2025) as well as Haugesund (population = 46,400), which is split between the municipalities of Karmøy and Haugesund.

Being the largest city in the area and a hub for many activities (e.g. employment and public services), Haugesund was selected as the primary location for the workshops. To further diversify the perspectives and offer an alternative to participants, workshop sessions were also scheduled in Kopervik.

2.3 Pilot site activities

The activities at the pilot sites include the following (see Figure 3):

- **Immersive 3D planning game:** an interactive scenario planning tool with immersive 3D visualisation designed to engage people and promote discussion about trade-offs, fears and expectations regarding wind power development (see deliverable 5.3 (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024))
- **Mental Models:** a method used to explore perceptions and understanding of the impacts of wind energy
- **Surveys and semi-structured interviews:** focused on project ramifications and acceptance (see deliverable 4.4 (Lowitzsch et al., 2024))
- **Other activities:** supplementary stakeholder engagement efforts aimed at collecting qualitative feedback on the WIMBY interactive map and forum, and broader insights into the projects overall

approach and methodology (see deliverable 5.1 (Bakelants et al., 2024))

Figure 3: Outline of activities at pilot region Karmøy (Graphic: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

The immersive 3D planning game was tailored to each specific pilot site and, together with the mental models, conducted during workshops with participants. Individuals were approached in public spaces, such as streets or local hotspots, for the interviews on project impacts and acceptance. In some cases, interviews were also conducted with workshop participants after the sessions concluded. Other activities included a brief presentation of the WIMBY Interactive Map and Forum, as well as semi-structured video interviews with selected stakeholders.

2.4 Immersive 3D Planning Game

2.4.1 Workshop Design and Data Collection

The planning game workshops aimed to explore potential wind energy developments through an interactive experience using immersive 3D visualisations and a planning game approach. For this purpose, the BOKU team developed an immersive 3D platform comprising three interacting components (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Core components of the immersive 3D platform developed for the four pilot sites within the WIMBY project (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024)

The data processing utilized free, open-source, site-specific data (see Table 1), which was enhanced through manual and semi-automatic optimisations and provided the foundation for the game board, the game logic, and the development of immersive 3D environment.

The serious game approach relied on three types of visual output:

- The **game table output**, which served as a playing area for creating wind energy scenarios and working with maps during the workshops, using simple game bricks as input device;
- The **projector output**, to present a dashboard with 3D visuals, key data and environmental details; and
- The **immersive VR output**, which allowed users to explore realistic visualisations of their envisaged wind energy scenarios using VR glasses.

For more information on the immersive 3D platform, see Deliverable D5.3 (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024).

The immersive 3D planning game workshops were divided into five stages:

1. **Welcoming and introduction**, including a briefing on the objectives and procedure of the workshop
2. **Baseline survey**
3. **Planning game and interaction with the 3D visualization**, where participants engaged with the platform
4. **Interactive discussions and summary of the workshop**, to reflect on outcomes and insights
5. **Debrief/feedback survey**

Data collection during the workshop focused on participant engagement, learning outcomes, and decision-making. A baseline survey (stage 2) assessed participants' knowledge, attitudes toward wind energy, and prior experience with participatory processes. A debrief and feedback survey at the end (stage 5) evaluated the 3D game's usability, learning impact, the immersive experience, and the overall process.

The immersive 3D planning game consists of two game phases, whereas game phase 1 addresses the identification of inclusion and exclusion zones and game phase 2 focuses on the virtually planning of windfarms to achieve given regional targets.

During the planning game, participants' statements, reasoning, questions, and concerns regarding game decisions were documented, with time stamps added to link them to specific game actions. Separate notes were also taken to record general observations of group dynamics and interactions during the game.

With the immersive 3D planning game, we aim to motivate the placement of virtual wind turbines and wind farms and encourage discussions using specific energy targets. The targets for Karmøy are aligned with the needs of the local aluminium factory as a major electricity consumer. The target was calculated assuming that local electricity generation would contribute to the self-sufficiency of the municipality and ensure access to affordable electricity for industry, as described in section. This "Clean industry" target aims to reach 1.35 TWh per annum of additional electricity generation. An intermediate target "On the way 2030" was also added, representing one third of the overarching goal.

2.4.2 Geospatial data sources

The immersive 3D environment used for the planning game workshops requires high-resolution and up-to-date datasets for accurate and close-to-reality visualisations. Table 1 presents all datasets used and processed to build the virtual environment and convey supplementary information. Norway's overall open-data availability and –coverage, combined with – in Norway highly precise – infrastructural data (buildings, roads, etc.) from OpenStreetMap, satisfied the needs for our visualization without accessing proprietary data.

Shaped by fjords, lakes, and rivers, Karmøy naturally features frequent ship traffic. To capture this, we estimated the position of boats and ships using the existing pier infrastructure extracted from OpenStreetMap.

Although the AR50 land cover dataset provides a good coverage of the area, it does not reflect the diversity of Norway's distinctive, extensive natural meadow landscapes. To increase the diversity of the virtual landscapes according to its real appearance, we use established GIS operations including the AR50 and DTM dataset (for slope and curvature derivatives) to extract important landcover details, namely wetlands and rocky formations.

Table 1: Datasets used for creating the 3D environment and game logic for the Karmøy pilot region

Category	Dataset	Source	Licence	URL/comment
True Colour Composite	Digital Orthophoto (DOP)	Norwegian Mapping Authority	Restricted, permission granted for WIMBY	https://www.kartverket.no/til-lands/flyfoto
Topography	Digital Surface Model (DSM)	Norwegian Mapping Authority	CC BY 4.0	https://hoydedata.no/LaserInnsyn2/
	Digital Terrain Model (DTM)	Norwegian Mapping Authority	CC BY 4.0	https://hoydedata.no/LaserInnsyn2/
	Normalized Digital Surface Model (nDSM)	Derivative of [DSM, DTM]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
Administrative	Digital Cadastral Map (DCM)	Norwegian Mapping Authority	CC BY 4.0	https://kartkatalog.geonorge.no/metadata/matrikkelen-eiendomskart-teig/74340c24-1c8a-4454-b813-bfe498e80f16?search=matrikkel
	Administrative Borders	OSM	ODbL	https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Tag%3aboundary%3Dadministrative
Land cover	AR50	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research	NLOD 1.0	https://www.nibio.no/tema/jord/arealressurser/ar50

	Small Woody Features	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	CC BY 4.0	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/small-woody-features/small-woody-features-2015?tab=download
	Improved Landcover	Derivate of [DTM, AR50] for wetlands and rocky formations	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
Infrastructure	Wind turbines	NVE	NLOD 2.0	https://temakart.nve.no/vindkraftverk
	Power lines	NVE	NLOD 2.0	https://temakart.nve.no/tema/nettanlegg
	Masts	NVE	NLOD 2.0	https://temakart.nve.no/tema/nettanlegg
	Extra Objects	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Estimated Ship Locations	Derivate of OSM pier objects	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
	Airports	Norwegian Mapping Authority	CC BY 4.0	https://kartkatalog.geonorge.no/metadata/lufthavn-flyplasser/8de1886c-2c54-4f1a-a527-566987ae7fbd
	Building footprints	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Roads	OSM	ODbL	https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:highway
Energy	Wind Capacity Factor	New European Windatlas (NEWA)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu
	Wind Speeds	New European Windatlas (NEWA)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu
	Potential for Wind Turbine Locations	Derivate of [DTM, Infrastructure, Wind Speeds]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
Environmental data	Protected areas	Norwegian Environment Agency	NLOD 2.0	https://kartkatalog.geonorge.no/metadata/naturvernomsraader/5857ec0a-8d2c-4cd8-baa2-0dc54ae213b4
	Particularly vulnerable areas in the sea	Norwegian Environment Agency	NLOD 1.0	https://kartkatalog.miljodirektoratet.no/Dataset/Details/702

	areas (SVO)			
	Seabird Wind farm Sensitivity Index	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research	NLOD 2.0	Available upon request.

2.4.3 Ecological data

Data on the sensitivity of seabirds (Wind farm Sensitivity Index, WSI) are derived from WIMBY deliverable 1.7 (Diengdoh et al., 2024) to estimate potential impacts of wind power on animals a specific location. The WSI is calculated based on nine vulnerability factors, representing the risk of seabirds colliding and/or being disturbed by wind power plants. The nine factors included are 1) *flight manoeuvrability*, 2) *flight altitude*, 3) *percent of time flying*, 4) *nocturnal flight activity*, 5) *disturbance by ship and helicopter traffic*, 6) *flexibility in habitat use*, 7) *biogeographical population size*, 8) *adult survival rate* and 9) *European threat and conservation status*. These factors make up a species sensitivity index, which together with information on the density or relative proportion of the relevant species in an area form the WSI. More details on the WSI methodology are available in Christensen-Dalsgaard et al. (2011) and Garthe and Hüppop (2004). The dataset originates from Norwegian Institute for Nature Research and is described in Fauchald et al. (2023).

Modifications were made to the dataset to improve the visualization for the participants. The original data shows the WSI at 10 km resolution, resulting in a low number of cells and very uniform data. The data was smoothed by taking the centroid of each grid cell and interpolating between them for a continuous representation of the WSI. Only the aggregated WSI across all species and seasons was included.

2.5 Mental Models

We investigated workshop participants' mental models of perceived wind energy impacts. Mental models explore individuals' cognitive representations of the external world, including perceptions of interrelations within a system and system components (Van Den Broek et al., 2025). To

elicit these mental models, we apply a standardised mental model tool called M-Tool, which allows participants to create their mental model by mapping relevant concepts, in our case, the perceived impacts of wind farms, and the directional relations as an influence diagram (Van Den Broek et al., 2021). We applied a two-step approach. In the first step, we compiled wind farm impacts from a literature review and from a survey with the target audience. In the survey, participants were asked about the impacts of wind farms that they could think of in all four pilot site countries to determine the most commonly perceived impacts. We analysed the open text responses where people described wind farm impacts following the guidelines on conducting thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2023). We applied a deductive or “theory-driven” approach, where produced codes are predefined through a theoretically informed interpretation by the researcher, in this case based on the impacts reported in relevant literature (Byrne, 2022). A selection of 20 impacts was made, comprising the most mentioned social, ecological, economic and energy production-related impacts (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Selection of impacts and the target variable (wind farm) used for the mental model exercise (Graphic: Leanda Vedder).

In the second step, participants could use these impacts to create their mental model by connecting them with each other or the target variable,

the wind farm in operation, with three weighted arrows, where the weight represents the strength of the influence between images (see Figure 6). Participants were handed tablets with headphones where they were first presented with an instruction video that explained the concepts and instructions of how to create their model, then they were prompted to create their mental model about impacts they expect or have experienced from wind farms. Afterwards, they filled in a short survey on their general attitude towards wind farms (on a scale from 0 = I fully oppose wind farms, to 100 = I fully support wind farms), their perspective on the energy transition and renewable energy policies. We applied a network analysis approach to analyse the data, where the impacts serve as nodes and the arrows represent the edges of the network. In this way, we investigate the most used impacts, the most used direct connections between concepts and the most used indirect connections for each case study. This allows us to gain insights into participants' understanding of the system, especially the indirect connections provide us with an understanding of participants' capability to conceptualise complex interrelations and systems thinking.

Figure 6: M-Tool mapping screen with a mental model created by a participant. (Graphic: Leanda Vedder).

The mental model exercise was implemented in conjunction with the 3D immersive environment during the workshops. To control for the potential

influence of the 3D experience on participants' perceptions of wind farm impacts, efforts were made to achieve an even distribution of participants completing the mental model task either before or after engaging with the 3D environment. This allocation was determined based on the specific workshop arrangements in each pilot region. In Norway, participants were similarly assigned to either complete the mental model exercise before (N=21) or after (N=21) the 3D immersive environment, maintaining a balanced distribution. Additionally, a high school group (N=29) participated solely in the mental model study and did not engage with the 3D environment.

2.6 Interviews on Project Ramifications and Acceptance

The term NIMBY (Not In My Back Yard) is widely used to describe local opposition to nearby developments, particularly those involving energy infrastructure such as wind turbines or transmission lines (Devine-Wright, 2009). As Brennan and Van Rensburg (2016) argue, negative externalities associated with wind energy projects (e.g., noise or visual intrusions) can foster NIMBYism. These localised externalities manifest in several ways. A concise review of the literature identifies four primary drivers of local resistance: (i) the environmental impacts of wind energy projects; (ii) their technical and physical characteristics; (iii) the distribution of costs and benefits related to the project; and (iv) the behaviour and practices of project developers.

With respect to **environmental impacts**, research highlights several key concerns: noise emissions (Langer et al., 2016, 2017); perceived levels of infrasound (Langer et al., 2018); the visual prominence of wind turbines (Langer et al., 2016, 2017); and their setback distances (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016); shadow flicker (Devine-Wright, 2005; Jensen et al., 2014); impacts on biodiversity (Ladenburg & Dubgaard, 2009) and property values (Jensen et al., 2014); grid expansion associated with projects (Langer et al., 2018); and the broader regional distribution of turbines (Bidwell, 2013).

Regarding **physical characteristics**, studies primarily focus on turbine height and the number of turbines. Brennan and Van Rensburg (2016), using a discrete choice experiment, found that higher turbines require greater compensation payments to ensure local acceptance. They also observed that residents demand increased compensation for each additional turbine

within a wind farm. Similarly, Langer et al. (2016) confirmed that the steady expansion of turbines in Bavaria, Germany, has intensified conflicts with local communities.

Research on the **distribution of costs and benefits** underscores the importance of perceived distributive justice (Ciupuliga & Cuppen, 2013; Huijts et al., 2012). Community benefits and financial participation have been shown to positively influence local acceptance (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Langer et al., 2017; Walter, 2014). Research suggests that community benefits are better apt to increase wind energy project acceptance than individual benefits (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Walker et al., 2014; Walter, 2014). However, many studies also detected cheaper electricity for locals as convincing benefit (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016; Cass et al., 2010). It should be noted that some residents might perceive financial benefits as bribery (Cass et al., 2010; Macdonald et al., 2017).

Finally, the **behaviour of wind energy developers** plays a crucial role in acceptance. Studies highlight that perceived trustworthiness strongly influences public attitudes (Graham et al., 2009; Jobert et al., 2007). Trust can be fostered by enhancing procedural justice, particularly through transparent and high-quality information (Zoll & Ackermann, 2001). Citizen participation is equally significant, with residents represented by local community members showing greater support for projects (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016; Corscadden et al., 2012; Langer et al., 2017; McLaren Loring, 2007; Upham & García Pérez, 2015).

Having the four aforementioned factors (i)–(iv) in mind, we addressed the following question: **Can certain project ramifications affect respondents' attitudes toward a wind energy project in the region and if so, to what extent?** To answer this, we gathered quantitative data through a survey with Likert Scale and semi-structured interview questions, assessing whether elements such as smaller turbine designs or financial compensation schemes influence local attitudes positively or negatively. By examining a variety of factors within one survey, this report provides a holistic review of their impact on local attitudes across different regions.

In a second step, we integrated these findings with respondents' general attitudes toward wind energy and their views on projects in their region. Research indicates that community benefits and financial participation

schemes can positively influence local acceptance, particularly among residents already favourably inclined toward wind energy (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Langer et al., 2017; Walter, 2014). Building on this assumption, we can explore a second question, namely: **Do project ramifications also affect the attitudes of respondents who are negatively inclined towards the project in the region?**

To analyse respondents' attitudes, we structured the questionnaire into three parts addressing their general attitude towards wind energy (Part I), their concrete attitude towards a wind energy project in the region, regardless of specific project characteristics (Part II), and their concrete attitude towards a wind energy project in the region, with defined project characteristics (Part III).

This approach follows Walter (2014), who differentiates between public attitude toward wind energy (general perceptions at the national level), attitude toward local wind energy projects (views on projects in one's vicinity irrespective of specific features), and local acceptance of wind energy projects (opinions on a specific project, considering its characteristics). A complete list of the questions posed in Parts I–III is provided in Annex I, with additional details on the design process available in WIMBY Deliverable 4.4 (Lowitzsch et al., 2024). Figure 7 provides a visualisation of the methodology.

Figure 7: Overview of methodological approach (Elaboration: Monika Bucha)

2.7 Other Activities

Each workshop envisioned additional stakeholder engagement activities, planned to collect qualitative feedback on the WIMBY Interactive map and Forum and any further insight about the overall project approach and methodology. Such activities were organised as follows:

- A short Interactive presentation of the WIMBY Interactive Map and Forum including a real-time simulation
- Semi-structured interviews to selected stakeholders

The presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and forum was provided to workshop participants whenever possible: presentations lasted from 5 to 10 minutes, and it included a real-time simulation guided by the direct interaction with attendants. At the end of the simulation, each participant could provide his/her informal feedback on the experience and suggest enhancements.

Semi-structured video interviews with selected stakeholders were conducted with a twofold objective: (i) to gather opinions and perspectives on wind energy and the local context that could enrich quantitative survey results with qualitative insights, and (ii) to ensure that local voices were heard and shared at the community level, fostering participation and exchange of views. To maximise visibility, once published, all links to the interviews were circulated among the relevant organisations and interviewees, and promoted through all WIMBY communication channels, always with prior consent.

To carry out the interviews, the Deep Blue team

- prepared a standard list of guiding questions (see Annex II), common to all pilot sites.
- identified potential candidates in advance by liaising with pilot site leaders.
- collected signed consent forms from interviewees, authorising both the recording and the publication of the videos on WIMBY communication channels
- planned 20-minute video-recording sessions.

Thanks to the informal setting and the open-ended questions, interviewees had the space to express their views freely. This allowed the team to capture

local nuances and perceptions of wind energy projects and renewable energy systems more broadly. After recording, a preliminary edited version was shared with participants and pilot site leaders for approval prior to publication. Highlights and key takeaways from the interviews are presented in section 3.4

In this case, the Deep Blue team could not be physically present to conduct the interviews. However, local partners and workshop organisers on-site successfully carried out the recordings, following the same procedure described above.

3. Results and Discussion

Between 6th and 8th May 2025, six workshops were organised in Haugesund and Kopervik. In Haugesund, 19 adults participated in four workshops, and in Kopervik, two workshops were held for a total of 27 school children. Participants in these locations participated in both the immersive 3D planning game and created mental models. Additionally, 25 school children in Haugesund created only mental models and gave feedback on the Interactive map. In addition to the participants who attended the workshops, 21 interviews were carried out around Haugesund.

The participants spanned members of environmental organisations, opposition groups, industry actors and university staff and students. Although there was a session with public sector and political participants scheduled, it was cancelled due to unsuccessful recruitment. Mentioned reasons for not participating were partly time limitations for such activities as well as overlapping with public events for the commemoration of the 80-year anniversary of the end of World War two (and occupation of Norway).

3.1 Immersive 3D Planning Game

This chapter presents the results of the two game phases, the analysis of the baseline survey and the workshop evaluation.

3.1.1 Game phase 1: Go and No-Go zones for Windfarm development

A total of 56 locations and regions were marked within the workshops with a strong opinion towards protecting settled areas and wildlife (see Figure 8).

Most of the participants preferred offshore regions far out in the North Sea to protect the vision from the mainland coast and to reduce impacts on seabirds (region 1). The centre region of Karmøy was controversially discussed as it is out of view from most larger settlements, but also a natural landscape that needs to be protected (region 2). Also, in the industrialized regions (region 3) there was no homogenous trend as there are also Viking heritage places alongside the industrial areas and attractive shipping routes in the East of Karmøy. There was a more uniform agreement in the eastern regions around Gismarvik and Tysvaer, where wind turbines already exist. Here, expansion/repowering was considered (region 7).

Figure 8: Distribution and density of Go and No-Go zones (Source: Open Street Map, Norwegian Mapping Authority, NVE, NIBIO, WIMBY; Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

This allocation process was accompanied by a discussion of the reasons behind it. The main arguments are presented in the following table (see Table 2).

Table 2: Major arguments (Pros and Cons) for the considered regions in the Karmøy pilot site

No.	Pros and cons
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1	Utsira: Far away from the mainland (visibility and reduction of seabird disturbance)
2	Karmøy Center: Remote and therefore not affecting many people but also important for tourism and nature
3	Håvik: Nearby industries but also close to settlements and in the vicinity of a Viking heritage spot
4	Ulvøya: Bird habitats and close to Haugesund
5	Haugesund, Norheim: Close to the larger towns and villages
6	Skudeneshavn: Settled area and important for tourism
7	Gismarvik: Existing wind parks and remote

3.1.2 Game phase 2: Virtual Windfarm development

The aim of game phase 2 was to develop specific wind farms based on the previously identified Go zones. By placing individual wind turbines or entire wind farms on the interactive game board, the effects on the landscape can be experienced in real-time in the 3D environment. In addition, indicators provide information about the effects on ecological factors at the selected location and the contribution of the wind turbines to the game objectives explained in Section 2.4 (based on turbine sizes and local wind conditions). With the help of VR glasses, immersive visualizations are also possible to better perceive realistic perspectives and proportions. According to the Go zones from game phase 1, three main regions were in scope for the establishment of wind farms in the region. Below, three different wind farm scenarios that were developed during the workshops are explained using fact sheets.

Scenario 1: “Far out in the North Sea”

The first example (see Figure 9) shows a wind farm with 17 MW offshore turbines close to the island of Utsira. The main reason for this decision was to keep a certain distance to the mainland as this zone is more sensitive for seabirds and to make it less visible for inhabitants and visitors of Karmøy. The visibility in front of the open sea horizon is highly dependent on the light condition (morning hours vs. evening). However, due to the large distance of approx. 25 km from Haugesund it is hardly visible from there.

Utsira

Offshore Windfarm close to Utsira

10 wind turbines
Capacity: 17 MW/turbine

Figure 9: Factsheet Scenario I: “Far out in the North Sea” (Source: Norwegian Mapping Authority, Open Street Map, WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Scenario 2: “Everything in one place”

The second virtual windfarm scenario demonstrates a solution for bundling all required turbines to reach the clean industry goals in the remote centre of Karmøy (see Figure 10 below). On this site, around 40 turbines with 6 MW are required to reach the regional goals for clean industry. However, there are some smaller villages which are visually affected by the windfarm, and there are also impacts on seabirds and wildlife possible as it mainly consists of natural habitats.

Karmøy Island

Onshore Windfarm in the remote center of the island

42 wind turbines
Capacity: 6 MW/turbine

Figure 10: Factsheet Scenario 2: “Everything in one place” (Source: Norwegian Mapping Authority, Open Street Map, WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Scenario 3: “Where wind turbines already stand”

The third scenario has a focus on the expansion of existing wind farms and the spatial coupling to the industry (see Figure 11). The three existing turbines in Gismarvik can be extended by another 15 turbines with 6 MW. This number of turbines is sufficient to stay on the pathway for renewable industries but for the full transformation (100% clean energy for the industry), additional wind farms in other regions are required as due to settlements and villages the space for wind farm development is limited in the Gismarvik region. The visualizations also show that the visual impact for the villages is significantly higher. Although, due to the proximity to existing infrastructure (powerlines, industry, etc.) most participants had the impression that it makes sense to expand wind power in this region.

Gismarvik

Expansion of an existing wind farm

15 wind turbines
Capacity: 6 MW/turbine

Figure 11: Factsheet Scenario 3: “Where wind turbines already stand” (Source: Norwegian Mapping Authority, Open Street Map, WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

3.1.3 Analysis of questionnaires

The collected questionnaires were entered into an Excel spreadsheet and analysed using SPSS. This section summarises the results of the baseline survey of adults, the baseline survey of pupils and the results of the debrief questionnaires completed by both groups.

Baseline Survey Adults

The respondents were on average 52 years old, 63.2 % of whom were male. Half of the respondents had a master's degree or PhD as their highest level of education. 44.4% of the working respondents were in full-time employment, while the proportion of retired people was 33.3%. Of the workshop participants (n=19), 26.3 % lived in Karmøy. Of the non-residents, 50% cited recreation/holidays as their connection to Karmøy. Almost 60% of those surveyed had professional experience with renewable energy, with half of these individuals having worked in the field for over ten years. The most common areas of activity were environmental organisations/NGOs (45.5%) and the energy industry and planning (36.4%). TV, radio, and newspapers were cited as preferred sources of information by 73.7% of respondents, followed by the internet and social media (68.4%) and academic journals (52.6%). – In contrast to the other case study regions 47.4% of participants in Karmøy also cited environmental organisations and NGOs as a personal source of information.

The workshop participants expressed reservations about the expansion of wind energy: over 40% were against it (see Figure 12a), and 47.4% refused to prioritise it in renewable initiatives. More than a quarter (26.3%) of respondents feel that they are not involved in the decision-making processes for wind energy projects (see Figure 12b). However, some (31.6%) are interested in participating in activities that support wind energy initiatives, and 47.4% have already been involved in wind energy projects. At the same time, around a third recognise the potential of wind energy for a sustainable energy supply in the region, but many doubt its effectiveness in meeting energy demand (see Figure 13c) and question the incentives for expansion. Despite minor concerns, over 40% of respondents have already actively campaigned against wind energy projects.

Figure 12: a): Do you generally support the expansion of wind energy? b) Do you feel involved in the decision-making processes related to wind energy projects in your region? c) How do you rate the level of public support for wind energy projects in Rogaland? (n=19)

Nevertheless, 47.4% of workshop participants believe that wind energy projects have a positive impact on the local area and economy, while 63.2% are concerned about the social and environmental impacts of these projects, particularly regarding biodiversity and landscape aesthetics (see Figure 13a). The vast majority (88.2%) consider the implementation of environmental impact assessments and mitigation measures for wind energy projects to be of great importance (see Figure 13b). 72.2% of workshop participants believe that there are research topics that should be considered important for the promotion of wind energy initiatives, prioritising the development of offshore wind energy and mitigating the impact on wildlife. 27.8 % rated the involvement of various interest groups (associations, citizens' initiatives, etc.) as being very important for the success of wind energy projects, and 50 % said that they would be willing to work in such groups to help overcome implementation challenges.

Figure 13: a) How do you assess the potential environmental impacts of wind power, particularly regarding biodiversity and landscape aesthetics? (n=19); b) How important is it to conduct environmental impact assessments and implement mitigation measures for wind energy projects? (n=17) and c) In your opinion, how effectively could wind energy meet the energy demand in your region? (n=19)

In Karmøy, respondents considered incentives for investment in renewable energy, as well as other measures and regulations such as independent impact assessments that take social aspects and infrastructure into account, and economic incentives for those affected, to be important. However, a few respondents felt that there should be no political support for wind energy, nor any regulations to promote its development. 52.7% of those surveyed rated public support for wind energy projects as low, while 36.8% were unsure (see Figure 12c). Social acceptance was also perceived as low by 68.4% of workshop participants.

27.8% of respondents believe that wind energy is beneficial in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, whereas over a third do not recognise any improvement in quality of life. For 68.4% of workshop participants, preserving habitats is essential for wind energy projects. Many emphasise the importance of involving the local population in decision-making processes regarding issues of location and environmental impact. 63.2% identified the variability of wind resources as the greatest technical challenge. According to the participants, the most likely motivators for switching to regionally generated renewable energy are economic and environmental benefits, with socio-economic benefits such as job creation and local investment being seen by some as an important factor in supporting wind energy projects.

Many believe offshore wind farms are less disruptive to landscapes compared to onshore ones (see Figure 14b) and advocate that Norway should use its oil and gas expertise to lead in offshore wind energy (see Figure 14a). However, concerns were raised about their impact on the marine environment (see Figure 15a) and endangered seabirds and bird migration (see Figure 15b). Opinions were divided on whether Norway should prioritize other technologies, with some advocating for alternatives like hydropower, geothermal energy, and nuclear power, while many remained neutral.

Figure 14: a) Norway has a competitive edge from the oil and gas sector and should use that to become a leader in offshore wind energy (n=19) b) Offshore wind farms are less disruptive to the landscape than onshore wind farms (n=18)

Figure 15: a) Impacts on the marine environment caused by the construction and operation are too high (n=19) b) Offshore wind farms are a major threat to endangered seabirds and bird migration (n=19)

Baseline Survey Students

The students surveyed in Karmøy were on average 18 years old, with the oldest 19 and the youngest 17. 53.8% were male, 42.3% female and 3.8% identified as diverse. 61.5% lived in a city or a town, 19.2% on the outskirts and 19.2% in the countryside.

Of the pupils surveyed, 85.2% sometimes talk to friends or family about renewable energy, and 88.9% have already learnt about it at school or through other activities (see Figure 16a). The internet and social media are the most common sources of information on renewable energy. Most pupils (81.5%) have visited a wind farm or seen wind turbines up close, and 88.9% are interested in learning more about how wind energy works. Nevertheless, half of the pupils felt poorly informed about wind energy (see Figure 16b). Some of the students were unable to evaluate photovoltaics in comparison to wind energy, for example, and could not answer questions about Norway's competitive advantage in the oil and gas sector and its benefits for wind energy, or about suitable locations for wind farms in their region.

Figure 16: a) Have you already learned something about renewable energy in school or through other activities? (n=27) b) I believe that I am well informed about wind energy. (n=26)

Nonetheless, the students surveyed perceived wind power as an important instrument for the energy transition and protecting the climate. Of the students surveyed, 48% believe that wind energy is important for the future energy supply (see Figure 17a), and 50% support its expansion (see Figure 17b). However, only 44% rated the sustainability of wind energy projects as high.

Although the majority (55.6%) said they could not assess public support for wind energy projects, 52% rated acceptance in their local community as moderate. Of the students surveyed, 59.3% believe that community

involvement is important for the success of wind energy projects, while 25.9% are concerned about possible negative social and environmental impacts (see Figure 17c). Many respondents believe that there are adverse effects on the landscape and scenery, as well as impacts on the marine environment and endangered seabirds, and problems caused by noise pollution. Conversely, some respondents see the creation of jobs and lower energy costs as potential benefits of wind energy.

Figure 17: a) Do you believe wind energy is important for our energy future? (n=25), b) Do you support the development of wind energy? (n=26), c): Are you concerned about potential social and environmental impacts of wind energy projects? (n=27)

Workshop Feedback

In Karmøy, 42.1% of adult workshop participants had experience with playing video games. However, over 50% were not familiar with serious games, and 47.4% had never used VR glasses. By contrast, almost 60% of the students had played video games, over 50% were familiar with serious games, and 83.3% had already used VR glasses.

Feedback on the workshop was predominantly positive from both adults and pupils:

A total of 63.2% of adult participants rated the wind energy game positively (see Figure 18a), finding the gaming experience appealing. Over 70% of participants found the group discussions conducive to knowledge sharing, and 57.9% found the 3D visualisations engaging and realistic. More than 60% rated the game's ease of use positively, and 50% found the visualisations helpful for understanding wind energy concepts and regional impacts (see Figure 18b). However, more than half of participants stated that the

workshop had not changed their attitude towards renewable energy, while 26.3% reported it increased their confidence in supporting wind energy initiatives (see Figure 18c). Many workshop participants would like to see more renewable energy initiatives and opportunities to participate in their community. Almost 80% said they would take part in similar workshops/events in future, and 84.2% also thought the simulation game would be suitable for other regional topics.

Figure 18: a) Overall, the experience of participating in a wind energy game was positive (n=19), b) The Game helped me to visualise possible regional wind energy scenarios (n=18) c) Did the workshop increase your confidence in supporting wind energy initiatives? (n=19)

Over 70% of participating students found the combination of role play and an educational game fun and interesting (see Figure 19a). 66.7% said it helped them to understand different perspectives, while 50% said it helped them to learn more about wind energy concepts, initiatives, and their impact on the local community (see Figure 19b). More than 40% said that the game had influenced their perception of and knowledge about renewable energy (see Figure 19c). Furthermore, 54.2% of students said that it had increased their confidence in wind energy initiatives. 66.7% of students found the graphic quality of the 3D visualisations appealing and realistic. Over 60% rated the instructions for the role-playing game, the 3D game, and the user interface as clear and user-friendly. Half of the students would like to see more renewable energy initiatives and engagement opportunities in their region. 58.3% would be interested in similar workshops or events in future.

Figure 19: a) The role-play combined with a learning game was enjoyable and interesting. (n=24), b) The game helped me better understand wind energy concepts and initiatives, as well as their potential impact on my community. (n=24), c) Did the workshop influence your knowledge and perceptions of renewable energy? (n=24)

3.2 Mental Models

In Karmøy, Norway, participants (N = 71) constructed relatively complex mental models, as they on average included more than half of the concepts they could choose from and connected them with on average more than one arrow, which reflects in the complexity measures of the mental models. They incorporated an average of 16.43 impacts (SD = 4.40) and 18.41 connections (SD = 6.03). The models predominantly emphasised environmental concerns, with the most frequently used concepts being Biodiversity Loss, Animal Fatalities, and Wildlife Disruption. Noise Emission was also among the commonly included impacts. Despite this environmental focus, the most frequently used direct link was between wind farms and sustainable energy, which illustrates that participants are recognising wind farms as a valuable source of renewable energy. This was followed by connections to Wildlife Disruption and Land Use Change. Indirect connections in the Karmøy sample spanned a broad spectrum of concerns (see Figure 20). The most frequently used indirect link connected Wildlife Disruption to Biodiversity Loss, followed by the connection from Sustainable Energy to CO₂ Reduction. Social dimensions were also present, particularly the indirect link between Social Debate and Justice for Local Communities. Support for wind energy in Karmøy exhibited considerable variability, with a mean value of 50.08 (SD = 28.48), reflecting a more ambivalent attitude

compared to the other case study sites. Notably, social impacts, particularly issues of fairness and the treatment of local communities, played a more prominent role in participants' models than in the other locations, where such concerns were rarely present.

Figure 20: Aggregated mental model of wind farm impacts among participants from Karmøy. The thickness of the arrows represents the total weight of the connections across individual mental models, with thicker arrows indicating stronger connections. Note: Only connections with an above-average aggregated weight are shown (Source: Mental model data, Graphic: Leanda Vedder).

3.3 Interviews on Project Ramifications and Acceptance

In total, 21 interviews (48% female, 52% male) were conducted in Karmøy, both during the workshops (see section 2.3) and in public spaces such as streets, churches, and municipal buildings. Some participants were contacted in advance via email and via phone to arrange a meeting, and interviews lasted between 15 – 60 minutes.

These interviews provided a small snapshot of local attitudes toward wind energy projects. Based on question (in the following: Q)1–8 (see Annex I), only one respondent opposed wind energy, 18 were neutral, and merely two were supportive (see Figure 21a). When asked directly about their feelings toward the construction of a hypothetical wind energy project in their vicinity (Q11), nine respondents expressed negative or very negative feelings (see Figure 21b, right pie). Interestingly, the majority of them considered project participation to be important or very important (Q12; see Figure 21b, left pie). This suggests that even individuals initially opposed to such projects may become more accepting if provided with meaningful opportunities for participation. This hypothesis will be examined further in the following paragraphs.

In the following, we will also focus on the impact of project adaptations on those that have expressed very negative, negative or neutral feelings towards a potential wind energy project in their region (n = 14). In the following, we refer to this group of respondents as sceptics.

Figure 21: a) General attitude towards wind energy (n = 21), b) Feelings towards wind energy projects and the importance to participate (n = 21)

The analysis of **Q13** (*Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?; see Annex I*) revealed that eight respondents supported altering wind turbine height, seven supported changes to setback distances, five favoured measures to prevent bird strikes, and three supported altering turbine numbers (see Figure 22, left pies). In other words, our study shows that up to 38% of respondents indicated increased support when technical adaptations addressed either (i) environmental impacts or (ii) the physical characteristics of wind energy projects.

Up to 29% of the respondents who indicated increased support towards a wind energy project in their region when technical adaptations were sceptics. This suggests that while some measures primarily strengthen support among those already convinced, certain adaptations can also influence sceptical respondents. Among the four technical measures in Q13, adjusting the turbine height was most effective, with 29% of sceptics indicating increased acceptance, followed by changing the number of turbines (14%), technical measures to prevent bird strikes (14%) and modifying setback distances (14%) (see Figure 22, right pies).

Figure 22: Technical changes which would increase one's willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 21)

Q14 (Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?; see Annex I) showed that financial participation was indeed appealing to certain respondents: seven respondents supported discounted electricity, six supported financial participation for their municipality, three preferred acquiring shares through external financing, and one supported acquiring shares with own funds (see Figure 23, left pies). In total, up to 33% of respondents were more willing to support a project when offered financial participation schemes; this directly addresses (iii) the distribution of ills and benefits.

Up to 44% of the respondents who increased support towards a wind energy project in their region when financial participation was offered were sceptics. Again, while some mechanisms appeal mainly to supporters, others appeal to sceptics as well. Offering the municipality financial participation proved most effective (44%), followed by discounted electricity (22%) (see Figure 23, right pies).

■ no answer ■ oppose ■ neutral ■ support

Figure 23: Financial participation mechanisms which would increase one’s willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 21)

For **Q15** (*Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?; see Annex I*), six preferred regular written updates, six favoured having a municipal representative on the board of directors, four respondents supported early involvement, and two favoured involvements in project implementation (see Figure 24, left pies). Overall, up to 29% of respondents showed increased willingness to support a project when given opportunities for active engagement in decision-making, indirectly depending on (iv) the behaviour of wind energy project developers.

Of respondents who increased support towards a wind energy project in their region when early engagement was offered, up to 44% were sceptics. Among the four measures, early involvement in planning and siting was most effective in appealing sceptics (44%), followed by granting an elected municipal representative a seat on the project’s board of directors (44%), regular written updates (33%), and participation in project implementation (11%) (see Figure 23, right pies).

Figure 24: Options for engagement in the decision-making processes which would increase one’s willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 21)

3.4 Other Activities

Presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and forum

The WIMBY interactive map was presented at the Kopervik high school and at a school in Haugesund (Vardafjell high school). The features and layers of the interactive Map were presented and questions regarding the design and limitations were answered. At both locations, the students had the opportunity to use their own laptops to try out the early version of the interactive map and give feedback on their experience exploring the map with the different layers but also creating a windfarm by drawing a polygon and experience the differences in energy production and the environmental impacts.

Video interviews

Overall, in Karmøy 6 video interviews were collected, plus one additional interview to the pilot site leader from UiO. All interviews can be found in the WIMBY YouTube playlist². The key messages are summarised in Table 3 below:

² <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLna5U7-OPgOtnOyUQbQhSDyjtFc8yE--p&si=vED0egy6ddPw1Va3>

Table 3: Summary of stakeholder interviews

Stakeholder	Description
Community member 1	<p>“Back in the early 2000s, I believed wind energy was a green solution and even supported local projects. But once construction began, I felt misled: neighbours were affected by noise, TV signals disappeared, and health issues emerged. Municipalities had little power to help developers.</p> <p>At first, I was sceptical about WIMBY workshops, but I found the day insightful and constructive. The visualization tools were well-designed and created a good atmosphere for open discussions.”</p>
Community member 2	<p>“Living near wind turbines has been challenging due to noise and other impacts. Attending the WIMBY workshop was a new experience for me. The presentation offered a fresh perspective, and trying the virtual reality glasses for the first time in years was impressive. It gave me a tangible sense of what projects look like on the ground, beyond just reading or hearing about them.”</p>
Community member 3	<p>“Generally, I believe wind energy, along with much other energy production, is unnecessary. Our economy doesn’t need to grow endlessly. Attending the WIMBY workshop was a new and positive experience for me. The project felt scientific, and the team communicated well making it a refreshing way to explore and discuss energy projects.”</p>
Student 1	<p>“I think wind energy is generally good, though it’s important to consider its impact on animals and the environment. The WIMBY workshop was really fun and engaging, especially using the VR glasses to visualize projects. It was great to participate, share my opinions on where turbines could go, and feel that the workshop encourages positive discussions about wind energy in the community.”</p>
Student 2	<p>“Of course, renewable energy is important, but I think other alternatives like hydropower are more effective for Norway. Wind turbines only produce energy about a third of the time, take up a lot of space, and can damage untouched nature. I liked the WIMBY workshop – the maps and interactive tools were a practical way to learn. But at times, it felt like the debate was too focused on wind and didn’t give room to discuss alternatives. For me, that reduces credibility. Wind can be part of the future, but it has to become more efficient if people are going to support it.”</p>
Teacher	<p>“I’m positive towards renewable energy, including wind, but I value our untouched nature even more. That makes me lean toward other energy sources rather than large wind farms. The WIMBY workshop was super interesting – my physics students got to role-play as mayors, developers, and critical citizens. It sparked</p>

	<p>lively debates and kept them engaged. The VR visualisations were especially effective in helping them understand the local impacts of wind power. I also appreciated the international dimension – students working in both English and Norwegian really gave it a global feel. I think the future will bring more solar panels, some offshore wind, and probably even nuclear power at some point.”</p>
<p>Karmøy pilot site leader and Associate Professor in Renewable Energy Systems at the University of Oslo</p>	<p>“This spring, we’ll run workshops in Rogaland where local communities can test our tools. One of the highlights is a 3D visualization game - you put on VR glasses and suddenly you’re standing in your own surroundings, seeing how turbines or other technologies would look in different locations. We’re developing interactive approaches where people can, for example, try to meet local energy demand or explore trade-offs between technologies and costs. The idea is to give participants real agency in the process, so their input doesn’t just stay local but can also feed into national and European policymaking.”</p>

4. Conclusion and recommendations

The objectives of the workshops were to engage local stakeholders in activities that challenged perspectives on wind energy deployment and to test the different tools developed in the project. To this end, a total of 92 individuals were engaged in one or more of the workshop activities.

There was somewhat of a polarisation in terms of support for wind energy among the participants. Results from the mental models showed an

average support of 50.08, on a scale of 0 to 100 (low to high) and a standard deviation of 28.48 indicating a large variability. Similarly, in the baseline survey, 42% of participants opposed wind energy, 21% were neutral and 37% positive. Interestingly, 86% of the interviewees were originally neutral towards wind energy when asked, but more negative (43%) when asked about a hypothetical project in their vicinity. Students were slightly more positive when surveyed on wind energy, with 50% supporting its expansion.

From both the questionnaires and the mental models, the environmental impact (biodiversity and wildlife impacts) of wind energy was perceived as high and important to avoid. At the same time, aspects of community involvement were found to be more important than in the other case study regions (Giorgi et al., 2025; Schauppenlehner et al., 2025; Serôdio et al., 2025). This could also be seen in the first phase of the immersive 3D planning game, when participants identified go and no-go areas. Locations such as Håvik and the centre of the island was contested with both pros and cons. Håvik was raised as a go area due to its grey areas and location near industries, but at the same time rejected due to its proximity to settlements and cultural heritage. Similarly, the centre of Karmøy was considered as important for tourism and nature (making it a no-go area) and at the same time remote and not affecting many people (making it a go area). Participants try to balance these two (sometimes conflicting) aspects. Offshore wind farms are perceived as less disruptive to the landscape, and a majority (68.4%) advocate that Norway should use its oil and gas expertise to become a leader in offshore wind energy (Figure 14a and b). However, concerns were also raised about their impact on the marine environment and bird migration (Figure 15a and b).

The surveys and semi-structured interviews (see section 3.3) indicate that certain project ramifications can significantly influence local attitudes towards a wind energy project, including among those initially opposed. The measures most effective in convincing respondents with negative views were adjusting the number and height of turbines, ensuring municipal financial participation, providing regular written updates on project progress, and involving stakeholders early in planning and siting processes.

The overall feedback from participants regarding the workshop activities was predominantly positive. Almost 80% were positive in taking part in similar workshops in the future as well as applying the visualisations and serious games approach for other topics. At the same time, the attitudes towards wind energy remained largely unchanged after the activities.

The findings suggest that employing a wide range of participation methods increases the likelihood of engaging a broader spectrum of residents. It is particularly important not only to be informed, but also to be able to participate in the planning process and make suggestions. Policymakers and planners are therefore advised to adopt a diverse set of methods – including early involvement, the use of realistic VR simulations, and financial participation schemes – to strengthen local trust and enhance project acceptance.

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ANNEX

Annex I: Survey and semi-structured interview conducted to assess the impact of project ramifications on respondent's concrete attitude towards wind energy projects

	Question	Answer	
PART I General attitude towards wind energy	1_Do you believe climate change is human-induced and that it is one of the biggest problems of our times?	1 (strongly disagree) 2 (disagree) 3 (neutral) 4 (agree) 5 (strongly agree)	
	2_ Regarding the environment do you agree that the protection of global biodiversity may require to accept worse conditions for local species?		
	3_Do you believe that our actions at the local level can make a difference to solving global problems?		
	4_Do you agree that everyone in your local society has a common responsibility to care for each other in challenging times?		
	5_When faced with a project challenge, do you prioritize finding the most effective solution regardless of cost?		
	6_When new technological innovations are introduced, do you think that debt should be taken on (with the associated risk) to explore and implement them?		
	7_Do feel that the problems relating to solving climate change issues are of too complex and that we lack the resources (time, training, etc.) to understand them?		
	8_Do you believe that radical changes, incl. technological advancements, (as opposed to traditional methods) are necessary to preserve our habitat and wellbeing?		
PART II Concrete attitude towards wind energy	9_How much do you know about Energy Transition in general?	1 (not informed at all) 2 (not well informed) 3 (moderately) 4 (well informed) 5 (very well informed)	
	10_Do you feel well-informed about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in your region?	1 (not at all) 2 (slightly) 3 (moderately) 4 (well) 5 (very well)	
	11_How do you feel about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in your region?	1 (very negative) 2 (negative) 3 (neutral) 4 (positive) 5 (very positive)	
	12_How important do you see your participation in the wind project?	1 (not important at all) 2 (not important) 3 (neutral) 4 (important) 5 (very important)	
PART III project ramifications	13_Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	A_change in setback distance	(i)
		B_technical measures to avoid bird strikes	
		C_change in turbine height	(ii)
		D_change in number of wind turbines	
		E_other	
	14_Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	A_discounted electricity / lower energy prices	(iii)
		B_possibility to acquire shares in the project with own money (dividends / appreciation of shares)	
		C_possibility to acquire shares in the project with credit from project (dividends / appreciation of shares)	
		D_financial participation of the municipality	
		E_other	
	A_regular written information on the project progress	(iv)	

	15_Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	B_early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (once per month / quarterly)	
		C_involvement in the project implementation phase possibly also during construction (once per month / quarterly)	
		D_being granted elected representative of the municipality on the board of directors of the project (actual operation of wind park)	
		E_other	

Annex II: Guiding questions for interviews with participants of workshop

- General perception** – What is your personal opinion on wind energy in general and its development in Europe?
- Local context** – How do you think wind energy could impact your community or region?
- Opportunities** – What benefits or opportunities do you see in the development of wind farms locally?
- Concerns** – Are there any aspects that worry you or that you think should be addressed more carefully (e.g. landscape, noise, biodiversity, tourism, health)?
- Social acceptance** – In your view, what factors could increase or decrease public acceptance of wind energy projects?
- Stakeholder involvement** – How do you think citizens and stakeholders should be involved in the decision-making processes?
- Support tools** – How useful do you find tools such as interactive maps or online forums to facilitate participation and understanding of projects?
- Fairness & benefits** – Do you think measures like financial compensation or community participation schemes could help build greater support?
- Personal experiences** – Have you had any direct or indirect experiences with wind projects? If yes, what worked well and what didn't?
- Future vision** – What role do you see for wind energy (and renewables in general) in the energy transition of your territory?

Annex III: Identified relevant stakeholders in Rogaland and Karmøy

Table 4: Identified stakeholders for the pilot site in Karmøy

Stakeholder	Geographical level
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Political and public organisations	
Avinor AS	National
Haugaland Vekst IKS	Local
Haugesund kommune	Local
Karmøy kommune	Local
Fagne	Regional
Statnett	National
Frømskrittspartiet Karmøy	Local
Karmøylista	Local
Karmøy Arbeidarparti	Local
Høyre Karmøy	Local
Karmøy Kristelig Folkeparti	Local
Industri- og Næringspartiet	Local
Senterpartiet	Local
Sosialistisk Venstreparti	Local
Venstre	Local
Miljøpartiet de Grønne	Local
Rødt	Local
Energidepartementet	National
Noregs vassdrags- og energidirektorat	National
Rogaland fylkeskommune	Regional
Statsforvalteren i Rogaland	Regional
Environmental organisations	
Norges Miljøvernforbund	National
BirdLife Norge	National
BirdLife Rogaland	Regional (Rogaland)
BirdLife Rogaland - Stavanger og omegn lokallag	Local (Stavanger og omegn)
BirdLife Rogaland - Jæren lokallag	Local (Jæren)
BirdLife Rogaland - Dalane lokallag	Local (Dalane)
BirdLife Rogaland - Haugaland lokallag	Local (Haugaland)
Naturvernforbundet	National
Naturvernforbundet - Strand lokallag	Local
Naturvernforbundet - Suldal lokallag	Local
Framtiden i våre hender	National
Miljøstiftelsen Bellona	National
Natur og ungdom	National
Natur og ungdom - Rogaland lokallag	Regional
Natur og ungdom - Haugalandet lokallag	Local
Lobbying groups	
Motvind Norge	National
Motvind Sørvest	Regional
Fornybar Norge	National
Industry	
Norges Rederiforbund	National

Unitech offshore AS	National
Solvind prosjekt AS	Regional
Statkraft	National
Zephyr AS	National
Tysvær vindpark AS	National
Marin Energi Testsenter AS	Local
Hydro Karmøy	Local
Karmøy Sveis & Landbruk	Local
Destinasjon Haugesund & Haugalandet AS	Local
NEI til havvind ved Utsira, Bokn og Karmøy på Haugalandet!	Local
Forum for Natur og Friluftsliv (FNF)	National
Forum for Natur og Friluftsliv (FNF) - Rogaland	Regional (Rogaland)
Norges Fiskarlag	National
Sør-Norges Fiskarlag	Regional
Karmøy Fiskarlag	Local
Den Norske Turistforening (DNT)	National
Haugesund Turistforening	Regional/Local
Sabima	National

